

FRAMING POLICE BRUTALITY: A STUDY OF NEWSPAPER COVERAGE IN NIGERIA

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Abstract: *The study examines Newspaper reportage of Police brutality in Nigeria. It adopted descriptive research design with the entire editions of the National publications of Punch and Nigerian Tribune newspapers from January 1st to September 30th, 2020. The publication content where analyzed with the aid of coding sheets. Findings from the study revealed that the Punch and Tribune newspapers frequently reported police brutality during the period of study. The study concludes that extrajudicial killings was the most common theme for police brutality reportage followed by harassment. The study recommends that newspapers should often report stories of the police brutality on the front pages in order to gain much attention.*

Introduction

Police brutality, in the form of the use of torture as an interrogative technique and other wanton abuses of human rights, remains one of the major flaws of the Nigeria Police Force, which has attracted public outrage and condemnation (Amnesty International, 2020). Police action has been particularly gruesome in their fight against crime, and the proliferation of anti-crime operations by the federal police has resulted in extrajudicial executions and degrading treatment in police detention centres throughout the country (CLEEN Foundation, 2018). General public concern over crime has increased the pressure on the police to arrest

many suspected criminals. However, this outcry by the public has also been used by the Nigerian police to systematically justify human rights violations as being an unavoidable part of the fight against crime (Human Rights Watch, 2019).

The activities of the police as an institution are meant to be guided at both national and international levels. In spite of state prohibitions against torture and misconduct by the police, torture has been reported as being commonly used in police custodies across Nigeria, which is a major reason behind deaths in custody (Network on Police Reform in Nigeria [NOPRIN], 2017). According to

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NOPRIN (2017), personnel of the Nigeria Police routinely carry out summary executions of persons accused or suspected of crime, rely on torture as a principal means of investigation, commit rape of both sexes, and engage in extortion at nearly every opportunity.

Therefore, there is a dire need to check this menace by organisations saddled with the task of curbing it. The media, as part of performing its watchdog function, is expected to bring such issues to public light as a form of information and education (McQuail, 2010). However, how well the media have performed this responsibility in Nigeria is a question that has remained unanswered? The way in which these crimes are reported in the print media has long been a subject of academic interest (Okafor, 2015). The mass media can furnish useful information to the people at large because they reach the largest section of society directly, indirectly, or through secondary readership and viewership (Dominick, 2011). Apart from the government and the people, another party that has a major role to play in addressing police brutality in Nigeria is the media. The media have been known worldwide to possess certain qualities that make their use imperative if the communication is aimed at a wider and heterogeneous audience (Oso, 2012). Since the media cannot be isolated in matters of police brutality, it is expected that they give prominence to such issues (Louw, 2010).

The newspaper, as a medium of mass communication, is very powerful in influencing

people through its agenda-setting abilities; newspapers set topics for public discussion (McCombs & Shaw, 1972). People mostly tend to live by what they see, listen to, or read from the media. The newspaper is mostly restricted to literate and financially capable members of society who can buy and read it (Okoro & Nwafor, 2013). Newspapers provide in-depth and interpretative information in the form of features, investigative reports, cartoons, special columns, and news analysis. They also provide permanence and convenience to readers, as they can be stored and read later, unlike radio and television, which are transient in nature (Asemah, 2011). Thus, the Nigerian press has a significant role to play in forming public dialogue that would help in social change (Oso, 2012).

Statement of the Problem

Newspapers play crucial role in keeping the public informed. Yet news outlet do not merely convey information, they also participate in the construction, maintenance and transmission of particular narratives and discourse. This becomes especially important in times of social issues as narratives about such issues may play a decisive role in influencing how people perceive them, including their causes and consequences and how policy-makers decide to deal with it.

The prevalence of Police brutality in Nigeria has been a major concern. Despite the fact that there has been a public outcry to end the menace, statistics reveal that there is still an

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increase in reported cases of Police brutality. The media plays a major role in sensitizing, informing and educating the public on social issues such as Police brutality. It is a platform for the education and information of the public in news worthy issues thereby performing its function of surveillance. However, the manner in which the media report issues such as Police brutality does not portray the desired level of advocacy nor urgency it deserves. It is against this backdrop that this study sought to evaluate the *Nigerian Tribune* and *the Punch* reportage of Police brutality in Nigeria.

Objectives of the Study

The main objective of the study is to assess newspapers' reportage on Police brutality between January 1st, 2020 and September 30th, 2020. Specifically, the study sought to:

1. Determine the frequency of reports on Police brutality in the *Punch* and *Nigerian Tribune* Newspapers
2. To examine the sources of stories on Police brutality in *Punch* and *Nigerian Tribune* newspapers.
3. To examine prominence given to stories of Police brutality in *Punch* and *Nigerian Tribune* newspapers under the period of study.

Research Questions

In the light of the above, the following research questions were raised:

1. What is the frequency at which the *Punch* and *Nigerian Tribune* carried Police brutality stories during the period under review?

2. What are the sources of Police brutality stories in *Punch* and *Nigerian Tribune* during the period of the study?

3. What is the prominence given to stories of Police brutality *Punch* and *Nigerian Tribune* during the period of the study?

Literature Review

Concept of Police brutality

Police brutality is the excessive and unwarranted use of force by law enforcement officers. It is an extreme form of police misconduct or violence and constitutes a civil rights violation (Amnesty International, 2020). The term also refers to situations where officers exercise undue or excessive force against a person. Acts of police violence include, but are not limited to, physical or verbal harassment, physical or mental injury, property damage, failure to act when required, and, in some cases, death (United Nations, 2021).

In the United States, qualified immunity is a legal doctrine that protects officers from litigation after incidents of police violence. This protection, issued by the Supreme Court in 1982, is often criticised for undermining the Civil Rights Act of 1871, otherwise known as 42 U.S.C. § 1983, which was designed to allow individuals to sue government officials for rights violations (Schwartz, 2018; National Police Accountability Project, 2020).

Mass Media and Police brutality reportage

Boadu (2012) posits that communication, undoubtedly, contributes to socio-economic

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development. The media, with their integrative and interactive abilities, have helped in shaping the socio-economic development of communities, countries, and the globe at large. Evidence abounds to show how the convergence of communication (as conveyed in mass media contents) and political leadership has affected socio-economic development, especially when development is viewed as social and material advancement or improvement in the quality of life, self-reliance, and improved living conditions (McQuail, 2010).

The mass media can furnish useful information to the people at large constantly because they reach the largest section of society directly or indirectly, or through secondary readership and viewership, regularly and intimately (Dominick, 2011). Apart from the government and the people, another party that has a major role to play in tackling police brutality in Nigeria is the media. Mboho (2005) adds that the media have been known worldwide to possess certain qualities that make their use imperative if the communication is aimed at a wider and heterogeneous audience. However, since the media cannot be isolated in matters of police brutality, it is expected that they give prominence to the issues of police brutality (Oso, 2012).

The newspaper, as a medium of mass communication, is very powerful in influencing people through its agenda-setting abilities; newspapers set topics for public discussion (McCombs & Shaw, 1972). People mostly tend

to live by what they see, listen to, or read from the media. The newspaper is mostly restricted to only the literate and financially strong members of society who can buy and read it (Okoro & Nwafor, 2013). The newspaper has an edge over radio and television due to its unique features. It provides in-depth news, investigative reports, cartoons, special columns, and news analysis. Also, newspapers provide permanence and convenience to readers; they can be stored for a long period and read at will, unlike radio and television which are transient in nature (Asemah, 2011). Thus, the Nigerian press has a role to play in forming public dialogue that would help in social change and provide interpretative information in the form of features and in-depth reports (Oso, 2012).

Nigerian Police's Brutality, Torture and Abuse of Human Right

The activities of the police as an institution are meant to be guided at the national and international level by conventions, standards, and treaties such as the Universal Declaration of Human Rights (1948), the International Covenant on Civil and Political Rights (1966), and the International Covenant on Economic, Social and Cultural Rights (1966). In spite of state prohibitions against torture and custodial misconduct by the police, torture has been reported as being commonly used in police custodies across Nigeria, which is a major reason behind deaths in custody (Amnesty International, 2020). According to the Network on Police Reform in Nigeria (NOPRIN, 2017),

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personnel of the Nigeria Police routinely carry out summary executions of persons accused or suspected of crime; rely on torture as a principal means of investigation; commit rape of both sexes; and engage in extortion at nearly every opportunity.

Violent treatment of accused persons by the police or other law enforcement officers is strongly against Article 5 of the Code of Conduct for Law Enforcement Officials adopted by the General Assembly of the United Nations, Resolution 34/169 of 17 December 1979, which states: “No law enforcement official may inflict, instigate or tolerate any act of torture or other cruel, inhuman or degrading treatment or punishment, nor may any law enforcement official invoke superior orders or exceptional circumstances such as a state of war or a threat of war, a threat to national security, internal political instability or any other public emergency as a justification of torture or other cruel, inhuman or degrading treatment or punishment” (United Nations, 1979, Article 5).

Constant and consistent reports are received from lawyers, human rights activists, social analysts, and journalists about police regularly demanding bribes, stealing, extorting money, and engaging in different forms of brutality and abuse of rights (Human Rights Watch, 2019; CLEEN Foundation, 2018). However, not many empirical studies have been conducted to provide detailed reports about the kinds of abuse and the level of brutality people face when they are arrested or detained by the police. This

may be due to the difficulty researcher’s encounter when embarking on this type of research, as gathering data from the police department is challenging because they may be unwilling to release such sensitive information (Okafor, 2015).

Theoretical Framework

Agenda-setting provides the theoretical backing for this study. The notion of agenda-setting started with Walter Lippmann’s observation that the mass media mediate between the world outside and the picture in our heads (Lippmann, 1922). Cohen (1963) asserted that the press is significantly more than a purveyor of information and opinion, stating that the press may not be successful much of the time in telling people what to think, but it is “stunningly successful in telling readers what to think about” (Cohen, 1963, p. 13). Lippmann’s and Cohen’s submissions were results of their personal observations, which lacked empirical footing. However, McCombs and Shaw (1972) established an empirical link between the media agenda and the public agenda in their seminal study during the 1968 U.S. presidential election. McCombs and Shaw (1972) opined that the mass media have the ability to transfer the salience of items on their news agenda to the public agenda. People tend to judge as important what the media judge as important. The media accomplish this by deciding what to place emphasis on in their news coverage, thereby setting the agenda of the day. McCombs and Shaw furthered their argument by showing

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that the mass media set the agenda for public discussion, using the outcome of their study of the American presidential election to advance a theory that has generated critical and sustained attention from researchers (McCombs, 2004). Central to agenda-setting theory is the idea that the media influence the level of importance people attach to what they see, read, or hear from the mass media. For example, by selecting certain events and ignoring others, and by determining how the selected events are reported, the media influence the public's perception of social reality (McQuail, 2010).

Agenda-setting theory is relevant to this study because if the media set the agenda for public discussion, it is assumed that sustained media coverage of police brutality will directly influence the level of importance the Nigerian public attaches to the issue. Therefore, the more attention the mass media devote to reporting issues of police brutality, the more likely the public will consider these issues to be important. As White (1950) argued, the world looks different to different people, depending not only on their personal interests but also on the "map" that is drawn for them by the writers, editors, and publishers whose work they consume.

Method of Study

Study Design

This study is conducted to analyze the reportage rates of Police brutality issues in Nigerian newspapers. For this study to be appropriately done, the content analysis method was selected.

Since the topic of the research is on analyzing Nigerian newspapers, therefore, only content analysis could be employed in generating quality results.

Study Population

Two widely circulated Nigerian newspapers namely: *the Punch* and the *Nigerian Tribune* were randomly selected by ballot for the study. These newspapers report current issues affecting the nation and they are sold at affordable prices. Also, they are easily accessible; they appeal to the audience and have a wide range of topics ranging from politics, health, entertainment, business and sport. The two newspapers are published every day even weekends.

Sample Size

A total of 443 newspapers were speculated as the total sample size for the two newspapers per year, since each of the newspapers is published once every day and nine months has no less than 270 days.

Sampling technique

The reports on Police brutality were searched for from page to page of each paper, and from 1st of January to 30th of September, 2020. The copies of Year 2020 Nigerian Tribune and the Punch newspapers were retrieved from Lead City University Library located in Ibadan, Nigeria.

Instrument of data collection

Content analysis method was used in analyzing the two newspapers to determine: the frequency of Police brutality stories in the selected

Nigerian newspapers, the prominence given to these stories, the genres or categories to which these stories belong and the areas of reportage of these stories.

Unit of analysis

The story categories of the Police brutality reported stories were examined as: News stories, Editorials, Features, and Opinions. The frequency reportage of Police brutality issues was determined by analyzing the total number of reports on Police brutality in the two selected newspapers for the chosen duration. The formula employed is $n/N \times 100/1$, where n = total number of Police brutality reports and N = total number of papers reviewed.

To examine the prominence or importance given to the stories by the newspapers, the following decisions were made: very important, which means stories are placed at the front pages of the newspapers; important, represents stories that are placed on the third page, centre-spread or back page of the newspapers; and least important represents stories that are written with less attention and, therefore, occupy other pages of the newspapers. To identify the reportage areas of police brutality, the following themes were generated: Extrajudicial killings, unlawful arrest, torture and harassment.

Methods of data presentation and analysis

The results were presented in tables and figures using frequency percentage tabulation.

Results

Table 1 shows the Police brutality reportage rate in the Punch newspaper from the month of January to September in year 2020. Out of the 213 Punch newspapers reviewed, only 69 carried police brutality reports. Thus, the Police brutality reportage rate in Punch newspaper was 32.4%. The highest reportage rate of 44% was obtained in the month of May while January had the least Police brutality reports.

Table 2 shows Police brutality reportage rates in the Nigerian Tribune newspaper from January to September in year 2020. The table reveals that out of the 230 Nigerian Tribune newspapers reviewed; only 36 carried Police brutality reports. Therefore, the overall Police brutality reportage rate in the Nigerian Tribune newspaper published in nine months was 15.7%. The highest reportage rate of 34.6% was obtained in the month of July while no Police brutality report was carried in the month of April.

The Police brutality reports in the two newspapers were classified into different genres or story categories namely: News stories, Editorials, Features and Opinions. Table 3 shows the frequencies of Police brutality reports according to different genres or story categories in Punch and Nigerian Tribune newspapers published from January to September, 2020. In the two newspapers, the news stories had the highest frequencies of 88.3% in Punch and 85.7% in Nigerian Tribune. Table 3 also 1 also shows that the two newspapers carried editorial

reports on Police brutality. The frequencies of features in the two newspapers were 4.7% in Punch and 7.8% in Nigerian Tribune.

The prominence given Police brutality reports can be categorized into placement of stories on front page, inside page and back page. Table 4 shows the frequencies of Police brutality reports according to prominence. The result in Table 4 shows that the two newspapers placed police brutality reports on the inside pages which had frequencies of 54.3% in Punch and 24.8% in Nigerian Tribune.

The Police brutality stories can be categorized according to their sources as in-house, private individuals, un-identified sources and news agencies. Fig. 3 shows the frequencies of Police stories in Punch and Nigerian Tribune according to sources. The result in the table 5 reveals that in-house was the most frequent

source of Police brutality reports with frequencies of 47.8% in Punch and 50% in Nigerian Tribune. Private individuals were the least sources of Police brutality stories in the two newspapers with frequencies of 4.3% in Punch and 11.1% in Nigerian Tribune.

Police brutality stories can further be classified according to the themes of their contents such as: Extrajudicial killings, harassment, torture, and unlawful arrest. Table 6 shows the frequencies of Police brutality stories in Punch and Nigerian Tribune according to themes. The result in table 6 reveals that the reports of extrajudicial killings had the highest frequency of 36.2% in Punch, 45.5% in Nigerian Tribune and 91.8% overall. Reports on torture had the least overall frequency of 28.5% in the two newspapers.

Table 1. Police brutality in some selected Punch newspapers

Months	Number of papers reviewed	Number of papers with Police brutality stories	%percentage
January	18	3	16.7
February	22	6	27.3
March	26	10	38.5
April	20	7	35
May	25	11	44
June	23	8	34.8
July	28	9	32.1
August	24	7	29.2
September	27	8	29.6
Total	213	69	32.4

Table 2. Police brutality in some selected Nigerian Tribune newspapers

Months	Number of papers reviewed	Number of papers with Police brutality stories	%percentage
January	27	4	14.8
February	23	2	8.7
March	26	7	26.9
April	22	0	0.0
May	28	5	17.9
June	24	1	4.2
July	26	9	34.6
August	25	2	8.0
September	29	6	20.7
Total	230	36	15.7

Table 3. Frequency of Police brutality reportage according to the story category in some Punch and Nigerian Tribune newspapers

Newspapers	Features	Editorial	Opinions	News	Total
The Punch	4(5.8%)	2(2.9%)	6(8.7%)	57(82.6%)	69(100%)
Nigeria Tribune	5(13.9%)	3(8.3%)	8(22.2%)	20(55.6%)	36(100%)
Total	9(8.6%)	5(4.8%)	14(13.3%)	77(73.3)	105

Table 4. Frequency of Police brutality reports according to prominence

Placement	The Punch	Nigeria Tribune	Total
Front Page	16(23.2%)	6(16.7%)	22(20.9%)
Inside Page	31(44.9%)	26(72.2%)	57(54.3%)
Back Page	22(31.9%)	4(11.1%)	26(24.8%)
Total	69(100%)	36(100%)	105(100%)

Table 5. Frequency of Police brutality reportage according to sources

Sources	The Punch	Nigeria Tribune	Total
In-house	33(47.8%)	18(50%)	51(50.1%)
Private individual	3(4.3%)	4(11.1%)	7(6.7%)
Un-identified	12(17.4%)	3(8.3%)	15(14.3%)
News agencies	21(30.4%)	11(30.6%)	32(30.5%)

Total	69(100%)	36(100%)	105(100%)
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Table 6. Frequencies of Police brutality stories in Punch and Nigerian Tribune according to themes

Content Categories	The Punch	Nigeria Tribune	Total
Extrajudicial Killings	25(36.2%)	20(55.6%)	45(42.3%)
Unlawful arrest	11(16%)	7(19.4%)	18(17.1%)
Torture	12(17.4%)	4(11.1%)	16(15.2%)
Harassment	21(30.4%)	5(13.9%)	27(25.7%)
Total	69(100%)	36(100%)	105(100%)

Discussion of Findings

Frequency of reportage on issues of Police brutality

Providing answers to the first research question how the Punch and Nigerian Tribune covers stories of Police brutality. The study found that stories of police brutality were reported frequently, considering the volume of stories carried in the selected newspaper during the period under study. The Punch had (32.4%) while the Nigeria Tribune had (15.7%). Looking at the unit of analysis; majority of the coverage by the selected newspaper were on the news stories with 88.3%, Features 12%, Editorial 3% and Opinions 11%. The results also reveals that the four themes of Police brutality reports, extrajudicial killings received the highest reporting with 91.8% followed by harassment with 44.1%. The findings agree with the assertions of McCombs and Shaw which opined that the mass media have the ability to transfer the salience of items on their news agenda for

the public agenda. People judge important what the media judges as important. The media does that by deciding what to place emphasis on in their news pages thereby the media set the agenda of the day.

Sources of reports on Police Brutality

In providing answers for the research question, the study found that the sources of stories on Police brutality reported by the selected dailies were mostly in-house sources with 97.8% followed by news agencies 61% with the least sources from private individuals 15.4%. Hypothetically, the newspaper as a medium of mass communication is very powerful in influencing people through its agenda setting abilities; the newspaper set topics for public discussion. People mostly tend to live by what they see, listen or read from the media.

Prominence given to stories of Police brutality

In finding answers for the level of prominence given stories of Police brutality in the selected newspapers, finding from table 6 shows that out

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of 105 stories; only 21% items appeared on the front pages, while 25.8% items appeared on the back pages. The inside pages contained more stories on Police brutality than the front and back pages. The inside pages carried 54.3% items. The paper reveals that the inside pages have the highest frequency of the reports on Police brutality, the back pages reveal the second whole front page where the least reports. The findings revealed that the Punch and the Nigerian Tribune newspapers report on Police brutality mainly in the inside pages. The findings corroborates agenda setting theory which states that the more attention the mass media devote to reporting issues of Police brutality the more likely the public will consider these issues to be important.

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Conclusion

From the finding of this study it is concluded that the Nigerian Tribune and Punch newspapers frequently reported stories on brutality during the period of study. Finally, extra judicial killings was most common form of police brutality followed by harassment.

Recommendations

Based on the research findings, the following recommendations are thereby made;

1. Newspapers should report stories of police brutality on their front pages, in other to create the much needed awareness.
2. Newspapers should often write editorials on the different aspect of police brutality as a way of informing relevant authorities and the public.

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